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Health Communication in Patient Handling at The Emergency Department of The General Hospital Dr. H. Yulidin Away South Aceh District

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Abstract

This study was conducted to look at health communication in patient management in the emergency department, where health communication is very important in providing action to emergency patients. Because if there is an error in communication, it will cause fatal to the patient. This research was conducted at the Emergency Department of Dr. H. Yulidin Away General Hospital. The method in this study uses qualitative methods with data collection techniques through observation, interviews, and observation. The subjects of this study were 18 people, of which 3 doctors, 5 nurses, 4 patients and 6 patients' families. The results of this study indicate that communication in patient management between medical personnel with patients and patients' families is effective in providing information. There are two types of communication used, namely verbal communication used such as oral communication that is easily understood by patients and families of patients, while nonverbal communication such as smiles, using soft voice intonations, and happy facial expressions when visiting patients so as to make patients feel comfortable with the services provided by medical personnel. In addition, in the Emergency Department, communication used to patients and families of patients can reduce and even eliminate the panic of patients who enter the emergency room in a critical and panic state, medical personnel tend to communicate so that patients and families of patients are calmer.

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Page 006-010

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INTRODUCTION

A hospital is a facility that prioritizes healing, and recovery efforts to the community. People come to the hospital for treatment and to get medical healing. The atmosphere of the hospital with inpatients, outpatients, and patients who can be referred makes the hospital situation crowded, many referral patients who have not received space and cannot be taken medical action.

Hospitals have a form of medical service which is a care service and treatment service. Often people say that hospital services are unsatisfactory, so hospital services must be improved. In a form of medical service, communication is needed, especially medical personnel. Therefore, medical personnel must have effective communication skills, both with medical personnel, patients, and patient families.

The hospital as a living social container in the form of an organization is a place of society, a place to live, and develop with a reciprocal relationship. This means that the hospital and the community have an inseparable relationship. Both have a give and take relationship. In the process of this reciprocal relationship, there is a communication that usually occurs between doctors and paramedics and patients (Erik P. Ekholm, 1981).

Communication in the Emergency Department can facilitate, accelerate the delivery and receipt of information in handling patients with emergency conditions appropriately. So that risks, threats or fatal consequences do not occur in taking medical action. Medical personnel who have communication skills with patients and families of patients to explain the conditions that are happening by not adding anxiety and providing verbal and nonverbal support. Communication also plays a role in facilitating patient administration.

From the description above, it can be concluded that the importance of health communication in handling emergency patients. So the communication will take place well if the people involved have the same meaning about something that is communicated. Based on the background explanation above, the authors formulate several problems, namely: 1. How is the patient handling process at the Emergency Department of Dr. H. Yulidin Away General Hospital, South Aceh Regency? 2. How is the communication model of medical personnel with patients and patient families in handling emergency conditions at Dr. H. Yulidin Away General Hospital?

The objectives to be studied in this study are: 1. To find out the patient handling process at the Emergency Department of Dr. H. Yulidin Away General Hospital, South Aceh Regency. 2. To find out the communication model of medical personnel with patients and families of patients in handling emergency conditions at Dr. H. Yulidin Away General Hospital.

METHOD

To obtain the results needed in writing scientific papers, research methods are very decisive for effective and systematic research. A method is a procedure or way of knowing something that has systematic steps (Husaini Usman, 2009). As for the method in this research, the author uses a qualitative method. Where the author goes directly to the field looking for data and information related to the problem discussed, namely "Health Communication in Handling Patients at the Emergency Department of Dr. H. Yulidin Away General Hospital, South Aceh Regency" Qualitative research is research that intends to understand phenomena about what is experienced by research subjects such as behavior, perceptions, motivations, actions and others.

Holistically and by means of descriptions in the form of words and language, in a special natural context and by utilizing various scientific methods (Lexy J. Meoleong, 2010).

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Communication is unavoidable, because communication is a very fundamental activity in society. People always try to find social interaction. When interaction occurs communication cannot be avoided and will lead to social contact. The doctor's meeting with the patient requires that both give each other the ability to transform messages. The form of communication that occurs when there is an interview conducted during patient handling. All behavior in the ongoing communication event has the potential as a message, because communication is an effective transaction to convey goals and intentions.

As said by the three doctors interviewed by the author, doctors conduct interviews and examinations with patients, then they provide clear information about the patient's condition. This is in accordance with the paternalistic model where doctors control the flow of information to patients and decide on treatment. The following are the results of the author's interview with Dr. Gajah: "The doctor communicates information about the patient after conducting an interview and examination of the patient, then communicates what the illness is, if he can be treated, we treat him, if further action is needed, we refer him. So, we give clear information to the patient and the patient's family in undergoing further treatment". From the above, it can be seen that doctors conduct interviews and examinations.

The initial information obtained is then used as material for diagnosing and determining the actions needed in handling the patient. Good communication is needed so that patients want to tell the pain or complaints felt by the patient clearly and honestly. The following are the results of the interview with Dr. Odi: "If the patient is critical, the communication will be later because seeing the emergency condition, prioritize the action first after taking action, then the communication will occur. Trying to find out the patient's complaints by asking the patient and the patient's family for further action. The communication must be open in order to know what the patient feels. After conducting the examination, We explain everything to the patient and the patient's family about what action will be given to the patient, whether the patient should be operated on. Because what doctors do is choose a set of information to communicate, then create a message and explain it using both verbal and nonverbal communication such as sign language, facial expressions, or pictures.

In addition, doctors can respond to patients and their families in a state of panic. Every time an individual feels pain with their illness, this will cause anxiety in itself. With good communication, it can influence the patient's emotions in making decisions to take action. "Dr. Gajah also added to motivate patients, explaining that all of this is a trial, all diseases have a cure, unless it is the will of Allah SWT, basically this ordeal is indeed heavy, but God willing, we can recover, we just give encouragement to patients." Health communication with patients or sufferers includes information related to individual health conditions, information on how to maximize care and how to provide therapy. Health communication to patients/sufferers is more therapeutic in nature which means facilitating the healing process. Therapeutic health communication aims to help patients reduce the burden of feelings and thoughts and help patients take action to change the existing situation when needed by the patient. And help reduce the patient's doubts and help the patient take effective action.

In addition, motivation must often be given by medical personnel to emergency patients, because this can foster an attitude of patience to patients in dealing with the illness they experience. The following are the results of the interview with Dr. Odi: "To motivate patients, we as doctors only try our best for patients and only Allah SWT can decide." Communication between patients and medical personnel is a major part of medical services.

Effective communication is very important in understanding the various problems experienced by patients. As stated by Dr. Gajah as follows: "Communication is very important in the patient handling process because if communication does not exist, there will be errors in diagnosing the patient's illness. The important role of communication is inseparable from the role of a medical staff, how the role and function of medical staff towards the delivery of communication to suit the patient's condition, and understand what the patient feels. There are two types of communication used during the patient handling process, namely verbal communication in the form of interviews with patients while nonverbal communication by directly examining the complaints that patients feel. To build effective communication, there is training and it depends on our own willingness to do it or not, and if it is to respond to patients and families of patients who are anxious, panicked in an emergency, we will explain to them what is happening, we explain to them that we as medical personnel will handle it." Explaining to the patient about the disease and how to handle the patient's illness also requires effective communication. If there is a failure to convey information, the patient will not understand the medical examination.

This is in accordance with the expression by Dr. Neysa, following the results of the interview: In building effective communication, talk directly, if you need help with the staff here, just say it because this is direct action to the patient. A doctor as a good communicator must certainly have the characteristics that support the course of communication with patients. And if communication with the patient needs to interview the patient directly through the 5W1H element in order to know the patient's complaints. After knowing the patient's complaints, we explain all the actions taken to the patient, and the information we tell must be effective and easily understood by the patient and the patient's family." A doctor must also be able to convince the patient and the patient's family in dealing with emergency conditions, which is what Neysa's doctor did.

In communicating with patients, nurses at dr. H. Yulidin Away Hospital use the Partenalistic communication model, where medical personnel control the flow of information to patients, then medical personnel communication is also easily understood by patients. In this case, it includes verbal communication, namely the spoken word. In addition, nonverbal communication is shown through gestures, facial expressions, body language, and tone of voice. In establishing communication with patients, nurses use soft language, low voice intonation, and happy facial expressions when visiting patients, so that patients feel comfortable. From several nurses interviewed by researchers, they suggested that they had built good communication in handling emergency patients by explaining the actions that would be taken. The following are the results of the researcher's interview with Syella, the emergency room duty nurse.

CONCLUSION

Based on research conducted by the author for approximately two weeks from October 4 to October 17, 2016, regarding Health Communication in Patient Handling at the Emergency Department of Dr. H. Yulidin Away General Hospital, South Aceh Regency, by looking at the results of research in the field in the form of observations and interviews, it can be concluded between the following: 1. The process of handling emergency patients is in accordance with the SOP, where the patient handling service procedure starts from the triage room to the action according to the cases and the patient will be separated to another room and in accordance with the action procedure. 2. The communication model of medical personnel with patients and patients' families uses the Paternalistic model, where doctors control information to patients and patients' families to cut off treatment senders.

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